

FROM THE HISTORY OF THE FORMATION OF THE OSCE**Guliyev R.***Senior lecturer**Azerbaijan University of Languages**ORCID: 0000-0001-6975-4626***Abstract**

The article provides a comprehensive analysis of the history of the OSCE's formation. It notes that the Berlin and Cuban crises led the Eastern and Western blocs to "withdraw" from confrontation and resolve problems peacefully. Starting from the mid-1960s, proposals from both blocs to hold consultations on ensuring security in Europe increased. This idea began to be implemented with meetings held in the early 1970s.

The article aims to answer three main research questions. First, it determines the reasons and history of the path leading to the Helsinki process - the convening of the Conference on Security and Cooperation in Europe. Second, it identifies the goals and interests of the Western and Eastern blocs in convening the CSCE. Third, it examines the process of the CSCE's creation and its transformation into the OSCE - from Helsinki to Budapest. To answer these research questions, official OSCE documents were used, along with scientific literature in various languages.

The article concludes that the series of conferences resulting in the signing of the Helsinki Final Act was one of the most important factors in the Eastern Bloc's collapse. In particular, the human rights issues included in the third basket of the Helsinki Final Act provided significant advantages for the Western Bloc. The CSCE's main achievement was the signing of the "Convention on Conventional Armed Forces in Europe." The CSCE, which went through an organizational stage from 1990-1994, became the OSCE in 1995. The organization supported Westernization processes of the newly independent states in the former Soviet region and other former Eastern Bloc members in the post-Cold War period. Unfortunately, this organization lacks a mechanism to implement the documents it has adopted.

Keywords: CSCE, OSCE, Cold War, Helsinki Document, security.

Introduction - The threat to the preservation of peace in the world during the period between the two world wars, the emergence of ideas such as fascism and Nazism, which were aimed at strengthening the tendencies of aggression and did not exclude racial discrimination, and the bitter consequences they caused, forced the world states to think about a new world order and take steps to preserve peace and security during the Second World War. In order to eliminate the troubles brought by the world war, to preserve peace and international security, to resolve controversial issues without resorting to war, to revive the economy, as well as to protect democracy and human rights, the world states began to unite around various international organizations starting from the middle of the 20th century. The first step on this path was the establishment of the United Nations, a universal organization. Although the establishment and activities of this organization played an exceptional role in the peaceful end of imperialism and colonialism in the 1950s and 1960s, the declaration of independence of colonies in Asia and Africa in a parade, and the accession of newly formed states to the world community, the threat to peace between states continued to persist. It should be noted that the possession of nuclear weapons by the United States towards the end of the World War, and shortly after by the Soviet Union, as well as the transformation of socialism from a state to a system as a result of the Second World War, and the accession of Eastern European and Baltic states to this system, led to the formation of a bipolar world order. The confrontation between the former allies - the United States and the USSR, the conflicts of interest of these two states that began in Iran (Southern Azerbaijan) continued in Germany and later throughout

the world, becoming a constant threat to peace. The establishment of NATO and the Warsaw Pact, respectively, under the leadership of these two states, resulted in the growing tension continuing in the form of a "Cold War" in a number of cases, without turning into an open war. Although the main actors of the Cold War did not openly confront each other, they indirectly joined the war by supporting armed conflicts in Africa and Asia (Vietnam, South Korea, the Arab-Israeli conflict, etc.), while they were able to calmly resolve crises in Europe and the Caribbean (Berlin and Cuba) by stopping them on the verge of nuclear war. Undoubtedly, both the UN and the blocs played a certain role in preventing the "Cold War" from turning into armed conflict. However, the possibility of recurrence of crises indicated the need for new negotiations to further expand interstate cooperation, to reach a common denominator among the states included in these two poles, to protect human rights, and to discuss again the principles of the inviolability of the territorial integrity of states. This idea, which emerged in the 1960s, began to be implemented with meetings held in the early 1970s. The meetings held in Helsinki, Geneva and again in Helsinki (1975) took the name of the Conference on Security and Cooperation in Europe (CSCE). After the collapse of the socialist system and the emergence of a new world order, the CSCE, in response to the demands of the time, transformed into an organization that directed interstate relations in Europe from competition to cooperation and was called the OSCE [1, 3].

The article examines the history of the path leading to the Helsinki process and the factors that made it necessary, the goals and interests of the Western and Eastern blocs in convening the Conference on Security

and Cooperation in Europe, and the process of transforming the CSCE into the OSCE.

The road to the Helsinki process. As soon as the Second World War ended, it gave way to a new war - a war between systems and values. This ideological war between the Western world and the socialist system led by the USSR entered the scientific literature under the name of the "Cold War" [20]. Thus, the defining feature of Europe after the Second World War was its division into two opposing political and ideological camps. Each bloc had its own unique subsystems: NATO and the European Union in the West, and the Council for Mutual Economic Assistance and the Warsaw Pact in the East. These organizations provided their members with a framework for mutual support and collective development in competition with the system of rival powers. This was not only a consequence of the political fragmentation of Europe, but also its most obvious manifestation. They also contributed to the hardening of this division. Attempts to reach an agreement that would ensure security and stability in Europe in the bipolar international system established after the Second World War were made in the mid-1950s. One of the issues discussed at the meeting of the foreign ministers of the USA, USSR, Britain, and France held in Berlin in January-February 1954 was ensuring security in Europe. At this meeting, the USSR proposed for the first time to hold a conference on security in Europe. However, the USA and its allies were skeptical and rejected this proposal, since it was proposed as a replacement for NATO and did not provide for the participation of the USA [16, 19; 19]. This proposal was assessed as a maneuver of the Eastern bloc in order to prevent the entry of West Germany (FRG) into NATO [3; 6, 16]. In 1955, FRG was accepted into NATO. As a response, eight socialist countries of Europe held a conference on ensuring peace and security in Europe in Warsaw in 1955. The participants of the conference spoke in favor of the creation of a collective security system in Europe [2, 304]. The Warsaw Pact Organization was established by the agreement signed by the states participating in the conference. It is interesting that the preamble of the agreement establishing this organization, which was a military organization of the members of the socialist bloc, confirmed the participants' attempt to create a collective security system on the continent with the participation of all European states, regardless of their social structure, and required the implementation of necessary measures to maintain peace in Europe. It was also noted at the end of the agreement that this agreement (Warsaw) signed for this purpose would cease to be valid from the day a collective security system was created in Europe and the Pan-European Treaty on Collective Security came into force. It should be highlighted that in passing that the first article of the Warsaw Pact contained one of the principles that would later be enshrined in the Helsinki Final Act of the CSCE, which would be organized some time later: all all signatory states the agreement must resolve international disputes peacefully and refrain from the use of force. The remaining problems related to borders after the Paris Peace Conference, including the Berlin crises of 1948-49 and 1953, the desire to legitimize European

border lines and avoid the Cold War turning into an arms race in Europe, made the issue of convening a general European conference to solve the problems consistently relevant. In the late 1950s and early 1960s, two important crises occurred in East-West relations. In the late 1950s and early 1960s, two important crises occurred in East-West relations. The Third Berlin Crisis, which began in 1958, reached its peak in 1961 and resulted in the construction of the Berlin Wall, which became a symbol of the Cold War. The second crisis was the Cuban Missile Crisis of 1962. In particular, this crisis, which threatened a nuclear war, was resolved before it reached the point of war. The crises demonstrated the ability of the superpowers to dominate the territories they controlled, but also their inability to expand these areas. In a short period of time, two attempts by one superpower to expand at the expense of the other failed [11, 36-37]. The equality of the blocs between the East and the West and the threat of nuclear war led both sides to "de-escalate" and resolve problems peacefully. Starting from the 1960s, negotiations between the USSR, the USA and the Western European states on interstate political and economic relations, as well as international problems and cooperation in the field of security in Europe began to intensify. After the Cuban Missile Crisis, the "red telephone" line was launched as a new means of communication between the USA and the USSR. On the other hand, the USSR began to take steps to normalize relations with European states. This process was also stimulated by the change in the Soviet leadership. Starting from the mid-1960s, proposals for ensuring security in Europe increased. In January 1965, at a meeting of the Warsaw Pact Political Consultative Committee (WPPC), it was proposed to hold a meeting to determine measures to ensure collective security in Europe [2, 308-309]. In 1966, during the official visit of French President Charles de Gaulle to the USSR, a joint statement was adopted, emphasizing the need for European problems to be solved by the continental states themselves and the importance of reducing tensions. At the end of that year, one of the main issues discussed between the representatives of the two states was the convening of a meeting on security and cooperation in Europe. During mutual visits and meetings between Soviet and British statesmen in 1965-1967, the British side expressed its support for the idea of a Pan-European meeting. In April 1966, during the visit of the USSR Foreign Minister to Italy, this European state also supported the idea of convening a Pan-European Conference on Security and Cooperation [2, 309-323]. At its session in Bucharest in June 1966, the WPPC adopted a statement calling for increased trade and economic cooperation, containing specific proposals for reducing tensions in Europe, as well as a proposal to convene a Pan-European Conference to discuss issues of peace, security and cooperation in Europe without the participation of the United States and Canada [23]. Although the document also contained serious criticisms of the United States and West Germany, the governments of Western European states discussed the proposals in the statement. The Prague Spring of 1968 not only prevented this dialogue between the two blocs, but also increased the importance of the pan-European

meeting. In the late 1960s, in the improved political environment, NATO countries began to think about expanding the détente process in Europe [18]. It should be noted that the period of easing of Cold War tensions between the United States and the Soviet Union from the mid-1960s, the weakening of the confrontation between the two blocs and the strengthening of the negotiation process has been recorded in the scientific literature as the “détente process”. Although this process spanned the period from 1967 to 1979 [21], the beginning of the period is sometimes associated with the signing of the nuclear test ban treaty between the USSR, the USA, and the UK in 1963, and sometimes with the start of negotiations on SALT-1 (1969) [24]. This period is marked by increased trade and cooperation with the Soviet Union and the signing of the Strategic Arms Limitation Talks (SALT). The successful conduct of the SALT-1 negotiations between the USA and the USSR in 1972 can be considered one of the most important sources of inspiration for the CSCE [7, 224; 14, 71]. During the period of détente, the recognition of the eastern borders of the Federal Republic of Germany (FRG) with Poland and Czechoslovakia, its readiness to establish relations with the German Democratic Republic (GDR), the speech of US President Nixon calling on its rivals to engage in peaceful competition, and his visit to Moscow in 1972 to discuss a possible conference and arms reduction negotiations and the signing of the SALT I, the invitation of both German states to become members of the UN in 1973, and the recognition of the GDR by the US were positive steps towards ensuring security and stability in Europe and towards the realization of a pan-European conference. Undoubtedly, in this process, two major government changes in 1969 - the arrival of the Nixon administration in Washington and the coalition government of Willy Brandt in Bonn - strengthened the inter-bloc relationship to such an extent that the policy of negotiations became the dominant element between East and West. In March 1969, the Warsaw Pact countries issued an appeal to all European countries (the Budapest Appeal) to begin preparations for a pan-European conference, which was supported by Western powers. The project was also well received by social democratic parties, liberal media, churches and trade unions, and peace and disarmament movements. In 1969, the North Atlantic Council in Brussels responded to the Bucharest Declaration with a Declaration on European Security, which included environmental issues and the “human dimension”. The Bucharest and Brussels Declarations paved the way for the Helsinki Process [23].

Goals and Interests: In the 1960s and 1970s, there was a need to change the policy of pressure aimed at weakening the other side between NATO and the Warsaw Pact. Because the policy of continuous pressure had increased the cost of armaments. It was also clear that it was impossible to destroy the opposing bloc with this policy. The need to appease some groups in the West that supported the Eastern Bloc and were increasingly vocal had also become a necessity. During the period of détente, both blocs had some goals behind their intentions to improve relations, and these were generally strategies aimed at further weakening each

other by using the process of appeasement [15, 28]. Both the Western and Eastern bloc countries had certain goals and interests in convening a pan-European conference. The convening of a pan-European conference would have recognized the represented states as sovereign participants with equal rights and territorial sovereignty behind de facto recognized borders. The Soviet Union had long been striving for international recognition of the political order in Eastern Europe, including the statehood of the GDR. For Brezhnev, it was particularly important that the division of Germany into two states be officially accepted by the Western Bloc [5, 343; 14, 71]. Such recognition would also give Moscow a confirmation of its hegemonic position. The USSR also aimed to gain access to Western technology and to revive its stagnant economy [14, 71; 15, 29; 17, 346]. The additional benefits of the conference, such as opening the way for Western support for the modernization of the Soviet economy, provided an additional incentive to support this project. Everything that made the security conference attractive to the socialist camp seemed to work against it from the Western perspective. The map of this part of the continent was the result of the Red Army's victory in World War II, and the regimes there were the result of forced adaptation to the Soviet system. Since the beginning of the Cold War, Western policy had been entirely focused on presenting the situation in Central and Eastern Europe as temporary, incomplete, and reversible. They did not want to give the impression that they were now making **permanent** a temporary situation, which they had endured out of necessity, permanent. Thus, they were faced with a choice between "preventing the conference for now, holding it harmlessly, or organizing the conference in accordance with their own interests." But what were the West's own interests? On the eve of the conference, the main intentions of the Western participants were not to be divided, to come out **with** a united front with coordinated positions, and to gain the initiative at the negotiating table [11, 39-41]. In **my** opinion, one of the reasons for the Western countries' support for the idea of convening a pan-European conference lay in the essence of the détente process. Thus, in this process, we see that the parties **had grown** tired of the confrontation. The transition to the policy of détente was a change in methods, because it was not the objects of conflict themselves that changed, but the means of pursuing the conflict. Détente can be understood as a form in which interests in a given conflict situation are represented not by confrontational strategies and tools, but by cooperation. In this regard, it is undeniable that the Western block, one of the main goals of which was to break up the USSR, which was based on a one-party system and a strong administrative apparatus, saw the process of convening a pan-European conference as a means of peacefully dismantling what they viewed as a "prison of nations" through various means (economic, cultural, etc. cooperation). The Western block understood that the destruction of the USSR was impossible through a policy of constant pressure (a policy of tension). Instead, it was thought that by bringing the most sensitive aspects of the Eastern bloc—political, legal, social and economic issues—to the fore, the system

would collapse from within [15, 29]. It is no coincidence that France insisted that human rights should be an integral part of any possible conference. The main issue that the Western Bloc wanted to include in the Helsinki Final Act was respect for human rights and fundamental freedoms, and the free movement of individuals and ideas [8, 638-639; 14, 71]. At the meeting in Madrid, the US delegation tried to get the USSR to accept articles mainly related to human rights and disarmament. In particular, the introduction of new tanks by the USSR (the US was significantly lagging behind in this area) prompted the US to negotiate on disarmament [9, 91-107]. The Western countries wanted to use the meeting to promote liberalization in the socialist countries. However, none of the main players in either camp had radical goals. The USSR accepted the human rights provisions that were later used against itself in order to preserve the status quo and ensure its legitimacy under the Warsaw Pact [13, 390; 15, 30]. Although it was possible to imagine what the general results of the conference that would be convened for the European states could be, the specific results were uncertain. The main expectation was that a document would emerge that would meet the demands of both sides. Although the goals of recognizing the independence, equality, and self-determination of the Eastern European countries were present, they did not openly express this. The countries that pursued a policy of balance between the two blocs and sometimes got stuck in these policies, which were not part of the blocs (members of the Non-Aligned Movement — R.Q.), saw a possible process of softening between the parties as more in their interests [15, 29].

From Helsinki to Budapest - The Process of the Formation of the CSCE and Its Transformation into the OSCE. On May 5, 1969, the Finnish government sent a letter to the leaders of 32 European states, the USA, and Canada, offering its services for organizing the meeting. On June 9, 1969, the USSR announced its support for these proposals [2, 309-310]. In June 1970, at the meeting of the Foreign Ministers of the Warsaw Pact countries in Budapest, consent was expressed to the participation of the USA and Canada in the pan-European meeting. At the invitation of the Finnish government, multilateral discussions began on November 22, 1972, in Helsinki on the preparation for the Conference on Security and Cooperation in Europe. The 96 points of the "Final Recommendations" of the Helsinki Consultations were adopted by the Foreign Ministers of the participating states at a meeting held from 3 to 7 July 1973. This also marked the opening of the main conference. The second phase of work began in Geneva on 18 September 1973. All European states, with the exception of Albania, as well as the United States and Canada, participated. The result of these efforts was the Final Act of the Conference on Security and Cooperation in Europe. The Final Act was signed by the heads of state or government of 35 participating states at a ceremony in Helsinki on 1 August 1975 and attracted incredible international attention. The Helsinki Final Act was drawn up in the form of "three baskets" prepared by the British. Basket I was generally devoted to "security" issues, and its most important feature was the

definition of principles consisting of 10 articles (Decalogue) to be followed by the states that signed the Final Act. Basket II was related to cooperation in the economy, science, technology, and the environment. Basket III was related to humanitarian issues. It reflected issues related to human rights, freedom of travel, cultural exchange, and education. The core of this basket was the removal of obstacles to the freedom of movement of people, ideas, and information, which are assessed within the framework of human rights [14, 73]. The participating states recognized the "universal importance of human rights and fundamental freedoms". For the Western bloc, the most important achievement of the Helsinki Final Act was the acceptance by the USSR of the values contained in Basket III. The Soviet human rights movement was founded in 1967 under the leadership of nuclear physicist Andrei Sakharov. Sakharov held a picket in front of the court on the day of the Nobel Peace Prize presentation in 1975 and was not allowed to travel. Human rights defenders such as Sergei Kovalyov and Andrei Sakharov continued to be persecuted and pressured in the USSR. However, the Helsinki process gave vital legitimacy to human rights activists and the ideology of universal human rights, and played a crucial role in helping the system undermine itself in the USSR and all its Eastern European satellites [5, 343].

The issues contained in the third basket of the Helsinki Final Act are indeed considered to be one of the most important factors in the collapse of the Eastern Bloc. However, the then US Secretary of State Henry Kissinger admitted that they did not expect the third basket to have such an impact at that time [8, 663]. Richard Pipes, one of the most famous historians of the period, noted in his 1976 work "Soviet Strategy in Europe" that the Helsinki Final Act was a significant victory for the USSR and confirmed the USSR's influence in Eastern Europe [12]. At the same time, the acceptance by the USSR of the document, which provided for the possibility of changing the borders reflected in the Helsinki Final Act in accordance with international law and peacefully, at the insistence of West Germany, gave a special advantage to West Germany and the Western bloc in general, and this constituted one of the basic legal bases for the future unification of the two Germanys. The most important gain for the USSR in the Helsinki Final Act was the Western recognition of the status quo in Europe that had emerged after World War II [8, 644-648]. This situation was the legal recognition by the Western bloc of the existence of the Iron Curtain. The aim of the CSCE during the Cold War was to bridge the divide between East and West and to strengthen security through cooperation. When comparing the results of the conference with the intentions that both sides initially brought to the table, it seems that it came closer to fulfilling the expectations of the West than of the Eastern participants. The socialist states would have preferred a short final document that clearly confirmed the status quo and included provisions that would pave the way for the creation of a pan-European control institution. The Western states, on the other hand, were interested in maximizing the level of exchange and communication between East and West

while minimizing institutionalization. The GDR publication assessed the Final Act as follows: "The main political question of the territorial status quo in Europe was resolved once and for all, the inviolability of post-war borders was established in a multilateral context – both politically and in terms of international law – and the principles of peaceful coexistence for the whole of Europe were established" [11, 41]. The aim of the CSCE member states was to expand and deepen the process of détente in Europe, to strengthen security through cooperation, to improve relations between the parties to the conflict, and to increase mutual trust. These statements were reflected in the most important document of the conference process, the Helsinki Final Act, signed on 1 August 1975. The Helsinki Final Act did not "define" any new human rights and fundamental freedoms; it mainly reaffirmed provisions already enshrined in UN conventions [26]. However, the Helsinki talks made human rights and fundamental freedoms a central and legitimate theme of East-West relations and, more importantly, an element of security. As former Soviet Deputy Foreign Minister Anatoly Kovalev recently noted in his memoirs, "With the Helsinki Final Act, the people – each and every one of us – became subjects of international law and acquired the status of active participants in interstate relations." Thus, the Helsinki Final Act provided political and moral support to champions of democratic change in the East, such as Charter 77 in Czechoslovakia, Solidarity in Poland, Academician Sakharov, and other "dissidents" in Central and Eastern Europe [25]. The signatories of the Helsinki Final Act decided to continue the series of conferences. Despite the tense atmosphere of the conferences in Belgrade in 1977-78 and Madrid in 1980-1983, the Final Act achieved great progress in the field of military aspects of security. The Stockholm meeting stood out from the previous ones in terms of the decisions it adopted. Between January 17, 1984, and September 19, 1986, the Conference on Disarmament, Confidence- and Security-Building Measures in Europe was held in Stockholm, and as a result of the conference, the "Stockholm Declaration" was published. According to this declaration, the states that signed it were to inform other states about their large-scale military maneuvers and exercises [14, 74-75]. The announcement of the policy of perestroika in the USSR during the Vienna conference (1986-89) allowed for concrete progress. The proposal made by USSR Foreign Minister Shevardnadze at the beginning of the conference was of particular importance. He proposed convening a special session of the CSCE in Moscow dedicated to human rights. In 1990, the Copenhagen Conference on the Human Dimension adopted a very important document on human rights, democracy, and the rule of law, which is still valid today. The Vienna Conference in 1989 and the Copenhagen meeting of the CSCE Human Dimension Conference in 1990 created fundamental conditions for revolutionary changes in the USSR. The final stage of the Human Dimension Conference held in Moscow in September 1991 led to further progress in the field of human rights [25]. The first official document adopted by the CSCE at the end of the Cold War

was the "Copenhagen Document." The second important step taken after the Copenhagen Document, the Paris Summit of the CSCE, was one of the most significant signs of the end of the Cold War [14, 75]. At the Paris Summit of the CSCE Heads of State and Government held on November 19-21, 1990, the "Charter of Paris" was adopted, which put an end to the "period of confrontation and fragmentation of Europe." It fully developed the main elements of the concept of comprehensive security. The participating states did not only agree on such terms as human rights, democracy, and a market economy; they also agreed on the substance of these terms, thus creating the basis for a new relationship. One of the most important documents signed at the Paris Summit was the Convention on Conventional Armed Forces in Europe (CFE), the most comprehensive disarmament treaty in history, signed by 22 states, 16 of which were members of NATO and 6 of the Warsaw Pact [14, 75-76; 17, 349]. The Paris Charter for a New Europe contained the most solemn commitment to respect for human rights and fundamental freedoms [5, 343]. Even during the negotiations leading up to the Paris Charter, some participating states had demanded a decisive turn towards transforming the Conference into an organization.

After the 1990 Paris Charter, the first permanent institutions of the OSCE were established. These include the Free Election Bureau (now the Office for Democratic Institutions and Human Rights, headquartered in Warsaw), the Conflict Resolution Center in Vienna, and the Secretariat [22, 6-18]. As a result of the decisions taken at the Summit, the Paris CSCE Parliamentary Assembly was established on April 2-3, 1991 [10, 6]. In addition, three more political bodies of the OSCE were established: the Ministerial Council, consisting of the Ministers of Foreign Affairs of the OSCE participating States; the Committee of Senior Officials (since December 1994, the Supreme Leadership Council) to assist the Ministerial Council; and the regular Summit of Heads of State and Government of the OSCE participating States.

The conflicts and wars that arose as a result of the collapse of Yugoslavia and the USSR increased the need for the CSCE, and in this context, the CSCE began to accelerate the process of its institutionalization. In order to control conflicts, the Council of Ministers decided in 1991 to establish the "Berlin Mechanism" [14, 76]. At the Prague meeting of the CSCE (January 30-31, 1992), a document on the development of the institutions and structure of the CSCE was signed. Real progress towards institutionalization was achieved at the Helsinki Summit in 1992. In the Helsinki Document (1992), the participating states declared the CSCE a regional international organization. At the meeting held in Helsinki in 1992 under the title "The Challenge of Changing Times", a final document was adopted on the declaration and a package of decisions (the decisions were on the structure of the CSCE and its main areas of activity). In December 1992, the positions of High Commissioner on National Minorities and Secretary General were established to oversee OSCE peacekeeping missions and operations. Since December 1993, the OSCE Permanent Committee (since December 1994,

the Permanent Council) has been operating in Vienna, and it includes representatives of all participating States. Since July 1992, the OSCE Parliamentary Assembly has been operating. The OSCE Chairman-in-Office (the Minister of Foreign Affairs of the state where the last meeting of the Ministerial Council was held) is elected for a one-year term and provides overall leadership for its operational activities. The structures and institutions of the OSCE are designed to carry out specific tasks or specific task groups. The package of documents adopted at the Budapest meeting (December 5-6, 1994) laid the legal basis for the transition to a new stage in the activities and status of the CSCE as an international organization, and according to the relevant decision, the name "CSCE" was replaced by the name "OSCE" from January 1, 1995 [4, 79]. Thus, the CSCE turned into a permanent international organization - the OSCE. At the same time, the legal doctrine indicates that, in the true sense of the word, the process of full formation of the OSCE as an international regional organization has not yet been completed.

Conclusion: Since the middle of the 20th century, the idea emerged of preventing the "Cold War" from turning into an armed conflict, preserving the existing borders in Europe, and maintaining peace and security. Thus, having come a long way from the conference-type negotiations founded in the 1970s and formed only in the mid-1990s, the OSCE played an exceptional role in preserving peace and security on the old continent. The series of conferences that resulted in the signing of the Helsinki Final Act is considered one of the most important factors in the collapse of the Eastern Bloc. In particular, issues such as ensuring the freedom of movement of people, goods, and ideas, as well as human rights, which were included in the third basket of the Helsinki Final Act, provided significant advantages for the Western Bloc in terms of ending the Cold War in its favor. The main success of the CSCE, which emerged as a process of dialogue and cooperation during the Cold War, was to ensure the signing of the "Convention on Conventional Armed Forces in Europe" and remove Europe from the traditional threat environment. When the Warsaw Pact was established, its treaty stipulated that a collective security system would be established in Europe and that the Warsaw Pact would cease to be in force from the date of the entry into force of the Pan-European Treaty on Collective Security, which was implemented with the signing of the "Charter of Paris." After the collapse of the Soviet Union, the Russian Federation, which declared itself its successor, failed to achieve its desire to make the OSCE a central element of the European Security Architecture in order to reduce the role of NATO in Europe. The OSCE still retains its character as an important mechanism for the continuation of the process of dialogue and cooperation between the Russian Federation and the West on European security. The CSCE took on a very important mission in the post-Cold War period, this time supporting the Westernization (democratization) processes of the newly independent states in the former Soviet geography and other former members of the Eastern Bloc. Most of those OSCE member states be-

gan to establish bilateral or multilateral partnership relations with NATO and the EU, become members of the aforementioned organizations, and solve their problems in these organizations. This led to the process of political marginalization of the OSCE. Factors such as the organization's lack of any economic, military, and political deterrent power have led to its loss of trust among its members. Unfortunately, this organization, in addition to not having a mechanism to implement the documents it has adopted, does not have both effective tools and political will to pursue a "peace enforcement" policy. This is one of the factors that reduces the effectiveness of the organization's activities.

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